

Large-Scale Extraction of Canonical References: Challenges and Prospects

Matteo Romanello

École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne / Deutsches Archäologisches Institut

« Introduction »

Canonical references are the standard way of citing primary sources in Classics. Alongside references to papyri, inscriptions, manuscripts and museum objects, these references play a key role as they point to the very object of study – the classical texts. These references are found in great abundance in commentaries, critical editions, monographs and journal articles, but only in the case of monographs the cited passages are listed in a specific *index locorum*, usually found at the end of the volume. Yet, these indexes and their importance to classicists confirm the essential function played by such references as a direct entry point to bibliographic information.

What makes canonical references special, and worth of being investigated by means of computational methods, is that they have been essentially stable for the last three centuries. Provided that we find ways to capture such references automatically, it becomes possible to track how often scholars have cited classical texts. The working hypothesis here is that these references can work as a proxy of the attention devoted by scholars to classical texts; if we accept this hypothesis, the capturing of canonical references from a large and diachronic corpus like JSTOR opens up new perspectives for the study of scholarly text reception.

In this paper I discuss the challenges and prospects of the large-scale extraction of canonical references. The starting point for this work is a prototype system that I developed and used to mine such references from a sample of bibliographic reviews drawn from *L'Année Philologique* (APh). This system is described in section 3 where I also give some details about the accuracy of the extraction. In section 4 I discuss the preliminary findings of some work in progress aimed at using the same system to mine these references from the articles contained in JSTOR. Firstly, I focus on the technical challenges of tackling a much larger corpus than the one originally used to develop the prototype system. Secondly, I sketch out what are the prospects of using these citation data extracted automatically from a large and diachronic corpus like JSTOR.

« Related Work »

The problem of extracting references to secondary literature (i.e. modern publications) has been extensively been in the field of computer science; on the contrary, capturing references to primary sources has remained, until recently, a largely unexplored area of research. This situation is paradoxical given that roughly half of the citations contained within humanities publications refer to primary sources.¹

The importance of capturing such references, however, has long been known to classicists. In the early days of humanities computing, scholars had already discussed the benefits and implications of turning these references into hyperlinks, especially in relation to digital commentaries.² Later on, the potential of using these references to enable new ways of searching for bibliographic resources within digital libraries was also recognised.³ More recently, the work carried out in the context of the (still ongoing) Homer Multitext project has made an essential contribution towards the creation of protocols and services that can “understand” canonical references.⁴

In particular, the work presented in this paper builds upon one of these protocols: the Canonical Text Services (CTS).⁵ This protocol provides most importantly a set of identifiers to express canonical references in a machine-actionable way – the so-called CTS Uniform Resources Names (URNs) – and defines ways to retrieve the text corresponding to canonical citations from digital libraries like Perseus. This essential piece of digital infrastructure for research in classics has made it possible from a technical point of view to start tackling the problem of automatically capturing these references from text and turning them into CTS URNs.

Looking outside of classics and broadening slightly our scope to include quotations in addition to references, it is possible to find a few more projects that leverage citations as a way to gain new insights into the work of an author or into a large text corpus. The “Understanding Shakespeare” project, a joint collaboration between the JSTOR Labs and the Folger Shakespeare Library, demonstrated the potential of identifying automatically quotations of Shakespeare throughout articles in JSTOR. The project led to the development of a reading interface where users can search for publications that quote a specific passage of any shakespearean play.

¹□Wiberley Jr. (2010), p. 2199.

²□See McCarty (2002).

³□The idea of using canonical references to cluster publications contained in a digital library can be found in Rydberg-Cox (2006) (pp. 65-67). Crane, Seales, and Terras (2009) argued that a digital infrastructure for research in Classics needs to enable scholars to search for canonical references and other named entities of interest.

⁴□On the technical infrastructure of the Homer Multitext see Smith (2009), Smith (2010) and Smith and Blackwell (2012). See also the contribute by Churik N., Smith N. and Blackwell C. in this volume.

⁵□The technical documentation of the CTS protocol can be found at <http://cite-architecture.github.io/cts/>.

Another example comes from the “Towards a digital Dante Encyclopaedia” project.⁶ Instead of looking at quotations of a primary source within the secondary literature, researchers have marked up the quotations of other sources within a set of primary sources, in this case Dante’s works. Once the quotations have been conveniently marked up, scholars can explore various statistics about the authors quoted by Dante. A dedicated interface allows them to ask questions like “what are the authors quoted by Dante in the first book of *De Vulgari Eloquentia*” or “how are quotations of Aristotle distributed across Dante’s works”.⁷

« The Automatic Extraction of Canonical References »

« Rationale »

The prototype system discussed in this paper is based on the idea of modelling canonical citations as named entities, and their extraction as a problem of Named Entity Recognition (NER). The system extracts canonical references by following a three-step process mapped onto a typical NER workflow. This consists of the following steps:

1. **Extraction of named entities:** a) names of ancient authors; b) titles of works and c) references to specific text passages.
2. **Detection of relations between entities:** since a reference is represented as a relation between two entities, the canonical references are reconstructed from the entities found in the text. For example, the reference “Verg. *Aen.* 1, 33” is expressed as a relation between the entity identifying the cited text (in this case “Verg. *Aen.*”) and the entity indicating the citation scope (“1, 33”), namely the precise text passage being cited. Representing references as relations between entities makes it possible to handle consecutive as well as more discursive references, where the components of a reference may be found far from each other, thus making it impossible to represent the reference as a single entity.
3. **Disambiguation of named entities and relations:** the system tries to determine which authors, works and passages are referred to in the text, and assigns a CTS URN identifier to each entity and relation. The reference in the example above, for instance, will be assigned the URN “urn:cts:latinLit:phi0690.phi003:1.33”.

⁶□Bartalesi et al. (2015).

⁷□A similar project in the area of biblical studies is BIBLINDEX, an online database of biblical quotations found in early Christian literature. On this project and the tool it has produced see Mellerin (2013).

These three steps, preceded by a pre-processing phase, form an extraction pipeline that takes as input a plain text document and returns as output a list of the canonical references therein contained, each identified by its corresponding CTS URN (see Fig. 1).⁸

Figure 1: Overview of the information extraction pipeline.

Among the processing steps in this pipeline, the sentence segmentation deserves some special attention as it is both important and challenging at the same time. The automatic splitting of a text into sentences is usually considered a straightforward task in Natural Language Processing (NLP). However, the high density of abbreviations that characterise publications in domains such as Classics constitute a challenge for many NLP tools that are available for this purpose. In fact, the trailing dot of an abbreviation is easily mistaken as final stop signalling the end of a sentence, thus leading to a wrong segmentation of the text.

Despite the additional difficulty it causes, splitting texts into sentences is highly important, especially for the analysis of the extracted citations. Indeed, the co-occurrence of two or more citations within the same sentence may be an important indicator of their relatedness, thus making the sentence a unity of context that is granular enough to be meaningful (especially when the text is fairly long and contains many canonical references).⁹

⁸ For a more detailed description of this pipeline and for an in-depth discussion of its evaluation see Romanello (2015).

⁹ The computational analysis of literary style is another case where the sentence was found to constitute the smallest meaningful unity of analysis, see Allison et al. (2013).

« Implementation and Evaluation »

The reference extraction pipeline described in the previous section has been implemented in a prototype system by using a combination of several techniques, while for the pre-processing step already available software was employed.

A supervised machine learning approach was adopted for the extraction of named entities from text, as this makes the system more easily extendable to new types of entities (e.g. references to papyri or inscriptions) and adjustable to the characteristics of coherent sets of documents, provided that trained data are available. After evaluating three different algorithms – Conditional Random Fields (CRF), Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt) – CRF was chosen as it yielded (comparatively) the best results.

The detection of relations between named entities is performed by applying a set of user-defined rules to the stream of entities that were extracted from text. Sequences of entities that match against any of these rules are connected together, by means of relations, to form references.

Finally, the disambiguation of extracted entities and relations was implemented using a combination of approximate string matching and context-free grammars. The former is used to match the reference string (e.g. “Verg. Aen.”) against the corresponding record within a knowledge base containing unique identifiers and name variants of classical authors and works. The latter is used to transform the scope of the reference into a normalised form: for example, the indication “VI 273-81” (book 6, lines 273 to 281) becomes “6.273-6.281”.

Task	Precision	Recall	F₁ Score
Named entity extraction	79.24%	69.62%	73.88%
Relation detection	93.33%	91.87%	92.60%
Entity and relation disambiguation	61.04%	90.94%	73.05%

Table 1: The results of the evaluation for each step of the citation extraction process.

The accuracy of this implementation was evaluated against a set of abstracts drawn from *L'Année Philologique* (henceforth APh), a yearly bibliography that indexes virtually any publication of some relevance to research in Classics. Although not all APh abstracts contain canonical references, the abstracts of publications with a focus on text often contain an indication of the main text passages that the authors discussed (signalled in the text by means of canonical citations). The dataset used for the evaluation represents a small fraction of all the APh data: it contains about 30,000 words of text originating from 400 reviews that were drawn from a single APh volume out of the 80 volumes published to date.

The results of the evaluation are presented in Table 1, which provides the precision, recall and F1-score measured for each step of the citation extraction process.¹⁰ As emerged from the evaluation, two are the most challenging aspects of the extraction. First, the extraction of named entities that compose the canonical references is characterised by a relatively low recall, meaning that a considerable number of entities are missed by the system. Second, the system is not very precise in assigning the right identifier to each entity or relation. On closer inspection, the majority of errors is due to the fact that, in the current implementation, the context that surrounds the references is not taken into account for weighting and ranking the disambiguation candidates.

« Large-scale Extraction of Canonical References »

The system described in the previous section has been employed to capture canonical references from classics articles contained in JSTOR. Because of its size and nature, the processing of this data poses some technical challenges but it also opens up new research perspectives, both of which are discussed in what follows.

« The JSTOR Data »

The subset of JSTOR from which canonical references were extracted consists of the journal articles automatically classified as belonging to Classics. This classification, which is carried out by JSTOR by means of topic modelling, leads to the inclusion of a small percentage of false positives (i.e. articles that are actually not about Classics), as one can easily see by looking at some of the journal titles.¹¹ This dataset consists of some 138,000 articles for a total of approximately 860 million tokens and almost 35 million sentences; from which about three million references to authors, works and specific text passages were extracted (see Table 2). It should be noted that roughly 13% of the articles in this dataset currently failed to run through the extraction pipeline, mostly due to noisy OCR data (see section 4.2.2).

	Number
Total articles	138,821
Successfully processed articles	119,723
Sentences	34,853,399
Tokens	865,075,857
Extracted canonical references	1,649,868
Extracted author mentions	1,448,163
Extracted work mentions	4,665

¹⁰ Precision, recall and F-score are the standard measures used in the field of information retrieval to measure the accuracy of a system in performing a certain task (e.g. retrieval, classification, etc.).

¹¹□The dataset contains some articles published for example in the *British Journal of Industrial Medicine*, *Crustaceana* or *Econometrica*. These wrongly classified articles, however, have little to no effect on the data analysis, as they are very unlikely to contain references to classical authors or texts.

Table 2: Basic statistics about the JSTOR data.

« Challenges »

« Size »

Without entering the debate about whether a dataset of this size qualifies as “big data” or not, it was clear that some changes were needed to process this volume of data in a reasonable amount of time.¹² The original implementation of the pipeline described in the previous section did not make use of any parallel computation, as documents were processed one by one. The processing of all JSTOR data on a personal computer took several weeks to complete.

The first change made to speed up the processing was to parallelise the computation which required only small changes to the codebase. While the various steps of the pipeline need to be executed sequentially – the named entity recognition, for instance, cannot be performed before the Part of Speech tagging – each individual step can be executed in parallel. The second change was to move the processing to a high-performance computing infrastructure. This made it possible to distribute the computation over the 48 CPUs with which each cluster node is equipped, whereas the previously used laptop had 4 CPUs. These two changes helped to reduce the time needed to run the JSTOR data through the complete pipeline from “months” to “days” of computation.

In addition to different requirements in terms of software architecture and computing infrastructure, the size of the data required a different way of dealing with errors that may occur during the processing. In fact, checking and fixing the errors is simply not a feasible approach when dealing with millions of words of text. Instead, a certain margin of errors needs to be taken into account and, eventually, reduced at successive passes by using an incremental approach. Especially the poor quality of the Optical Character Recognition (OCR), as I shall clarify next, can lead to errors that are hard to anticipate.

« Noise »

A first type of noise that caused some issues for the reference extraction pipeline consists of OCR transcriptions of poor quality. The general approach I adopted was to accept the presence of OCR errors without trying to correct or recover them. However, one case where this approach becomes problematic is when characters wrongly recognised by the OCR software are transformed into sequences of characters that happen to have a special function within the software. This is the case with the sequences “\n” and “\t” that are used by some file formats to structure the data into a tabular form. Wrongly

¹² See Schöch (2013) for a discussion of “big data” definitions that takes into account the specificities of research data in the humanities.

recognised characters that happen to form one of such “reserved” sequences will cause the file not to be parsed (i.e. read) correctly.

A second type of noise is due to the fact that the JSTOR data lack of any structural markup about the different sections of an article (e.g. running headers, page numbers, footnotes, bibliography, etc.). Thus, it is not possible to explicitly exclude from the processing some article sections, as it would instead be desirable to be able to do. References to figures (e.g. “Fig. 1a”) provide an apt example of this type of noise. As it happens, the title of Tiberius’ rhetoric treatise *De figuris Demosthenicis* can be abbreviated as “Fig.” – and this information is contained in the knowledge base used to disambiguate the extracted references. As a result, the system extracted more than 134,000 (erroneous) references from the JSTOR articles, which were then corrected during the post-processing phase.¹³ Most importantly, what this example shows is how the “understanding” of references which are absolutely clear to the human reader can cause some issues to an automatic system.

« Variety of Citation Styles »

Another challenge of extracting canonical references from JSTOR articles derives from the greater variety of citation styles that these references follow. In fact, while the APh is rather homogeneous on this respect, due to the existence of a set of guidelines for the reviewers, the JSTOR articles often have slightly different ways of citing canonical texts.

These variations in the citation styles can be attributed essentially to three factors. First, the language of an article, as the abbreviations of ancient authors and works may vary from one language to another. Second, the time period in which an article was written: in fact, some practices – such as the use of roman numerals to indicate book numbers – can be more or less common depending on the period. Third, the audience and publication venue for which a given article is written: articles written for a highly specialised audience tend to display more concise (and thus obscure) abbreviations in the references, whereas in articles written for a more general audience is more common to spell out the name of the author and the title of the work cited.

Due to the lack of an ad-hoc training set, the canonical references are extracted from JSTOR articles by using a statistical model that was previously trained on the APh data.¹⁴ Due to the heterogeneity of citation styles that characterises JSTOR, classification errors may occur when a style not represented in the training data is encountered. An apt example of such errors is provided by the mentions of ancient works. According to the style followed by the APh, work titles are always enclosed by angle quotes

¹³□ This would be a disproportionately high number of references for a minor author, considered for example that there are about 20,000 references to Vergil’s *Aeneid*.

¹⁴□ This consideration applies to the steps performed using a machine learning approach (currently, only the extraction of named entities).

called Guillemets (“«” and “»”), but this is not the norm across JSTOR. As a result, only about 4,600 out of more than 3 million references constitute mentions of work titles. In other words, the degree to which ways of citing canonical texts may vary is a rather strong argument for the use of a supervised machine learning-based approach, whose main drawback remains the manual effort required to produce the training data.

« Prospects »

Notwithstanding the practical challenges outlined in the previous section, the extraction of canonical references from large-scale digital archives such as JSTOR offers new and exciting prospects for future research. In what follows I would like to consider in particular two of these prospects: the first concerns the use of canonical references to improve scholars’ ability of finding relevant publications for their research, while the second relates to the use of such references as proxies for the study of scholarly reception.

« Information Retrieval »

Although references and citations can be found in any scholarly publication across the disciplines, references to primary sources in the Classics are particularly important as they refer to the very objects of the research. These references constitute as such an essential entry point to bibliographic information for classicists, as confirmed also by the importance that *indices locorum* have in this field as a means of finding and retrieving information. However, none of the existing tools provide the ability to search through publications by the references they contain, meaning that the user interfaces for similar tools are yet to be imagined and designed. As a proof of concept of how these interfaces could look like I have implemented *Aeneid in JSTOR*¹⁵, a web application that allows users to find JSTOR articles containing quotations of or references to the Vergilian poem (see Fig. 2).

¹⁵The interface can be found at <http://www.aeneidinjstor.eu/>.

Figure 2: A screenshot of the *Aeneid in JSTOR* search interface.

The main idea behind this interface is to combine both distant and close reading into an interface enabling what Martin Müller (2014) has defined as *scalable reading*, namely a type of reading which moves constantly back and forth between these two perspectives. This search interface combines into a single view two distinct pieces of data: firstly, canonical references to the *Aeneid*, extracted using the system that I have described above, and, secondly, verbatim quotations of the poem that were extracted by using MatchMaker, a dedicated tool developed at the JSTOR Labs.¹⁶ The starting point for the user is a visual index of the *Aeneid*, displayed on the left. This index uses a heat map to visualise the density of references and quotations for a given section of the poem: the darker a given chunk is, the higher is its density of references and quotations.¹⁷ In this sense, the visual index can be used to identify at a glance sections of the text characterised by an especially high (or low) density of references and quotations. One can already see, for example, how the first half of the poem seems to be more quoted (and referred to) than the second half. Upon selection of a single text chunk, the corresponding Latin text (middle panel) and the matching articles in JSTOR (right panel) are displayed. For each matching article, a snippet of the passage containing the quotation (or reference) is showed.

¹⁶ <https://github.com/JSTOR-Labs/matchmaker>

¹⁷ For this implementation, the text of the *Aeneid* was divided into chunks of 50 lines each.

« Scholarly Text Reception »

In addition to information retrieval, the large-scale analysis of extracted canonical references can provide new insights into the scholarly text reception of classical texts, which investigates how ancient authors have received different interpretations and degrees of attention by scholars in different historical periods. Although scholars in this field do occasionally make use of quantitative evidence to support their hypotheses and theories, quantitative or data-driven studies are rare and remain essentially isolated, and this is arguably due to technical limitations and lack of data rather than methodological concerns.¹⁸

The underlying assumption for the use of canonical references in the study of reception is that their frequency can be used as an indicator – a proxy – to track the fortune of classical authors over time. In fact, these references can be seen as a specific kind of traces of the scholarly debate left by scholars within their publications. The fact that a passage was cited means that it was “studied” – or at the very least “used” – by some scholar at a certain point in time, thus providing a potential indicator of the author’s fortune.

The range of research questions this approach can be applied to is wide and varied. One could look at most cited authors over time in order to identify on a quantitative basis a “canon” of most studied authors, and then study if and how this canon varies over time. Or one could pick one specific literary genre – e.g. ancient historiography – and compare the citation trends within that genre.

But it is also possible to focus on a narrower number of authors whose fortunes are considered to be intertwined with one another. This is the case, for example, with Ovid and Vergil how it has been argued, from a literary reception perspective, by Ziolkowski (2009). Ovid and Vergil were always seen as embodying two opposing sets of values: the former, in virtue of his exile, incarnates the artist’s freedom from politics, while the latter personifies the values of *pietas* and *amor patriae*. As Ziolkowski has masterfully shown in his essay, the reception of both authors within 20th century literatures proceeded in alternating waves of fortune and influence. But does this hold true also for the scholarly reception of both authors? Is the popularity of these two authors among scholars characterised by the same dynamics of opposition and alternation? These are questions that we can now start to explore – or even attempt to answer – by means of the citation data extracted from JSTOR.

¹⁸ □ See for example Scheidel (1997), where the author analysed data (manually) gathered from *L'Année Philologique* to carry out a quantitative study of classical scholarship and scholarly reception.

Figure 3: Frequency of references to Ovid and Vergil per JSTOR article (10-year moving average).

If we plot the density of references to Ovid and Vergil per article, starting from the beginning of the 20th century, the diagram we obtain displays some striking similarities with the waves of reception described by Ziolkowski (see Fig. 3). He identified three waves of interest in the literary reception of Ovid: the first wave begins after the World War I and ends around the 1930s, when Vergil becomes celebrated by nationalistic ideologies as the poet of empire. A second wave of interest takes place after the second world war, but it has a rather short life and is soon replaced by an increased interest towards Vergil and Horace around the 1960s and 1970s. Finally, there is a third Ovidian wave in the late 1980s when he becomes an analogy for the contemporary writers occupied by themselves and is appropriated by the feminist movement. The second and third wave emerge rather distinctly from the frequency plot, while in the case of the first wave the opposition between the two authors is not as strong as depicted by Ziolkowski.

« Conclusion »

Despite being found in abundance within classics publication, canonical references have hitherto remained an underexploited piece of information, as manual indexing has long been the only option when compiling lists of cited passages. The ability of automatically capturing such references, which is

starting to become reality, puts us in the position of imagining new ways to leverage these citation data, as exemplified by the two prospects discussed in Section 4 – respectively, the use of these references in the context of systems for the retrieval of bibliographic information and the possibility of using them as a proxy of the attention that classical authors received by scholars over time. There remains, however, work to be done to improve the accuracy of the automatic extraction, and to make the system robust enough to handle noisy input data. The quality of the automatically extracted citations data is crucial as it has a direct effect on the data analysis, as the conclusions that we can draw from the data will always be as good as the data we used to produce them. The large scale of digital archives that we can now mine is, at the same time, a source of great challenges for the automatic extraction of references, but also what enables the macro-analysis of cultural phenomena like the scholarly reception of classical texts.

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